

Properties of Core Materials for Sandwich Structures

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KEYWORDS: Sandwich Structures, Core Materials, Stiffness Properties, Strength Properties

INTRODUCTION

Sandwich structures have been used in numerous aspects of aircraft construction and they are coming into widespread usage in marine applications. Typical sandwich structures are made up of two thin, stiff, strong faces separated by a very lightweight material known as the core. By choosing appropriate core materials based on intended applications, not only are sandwich panels able to achieve high stiffness, and strengths comparable to those of single solid panels, but also great savings in weight.

Cores serve several important functions. First, cores should be stiff enough in the out of plane direction that the faces remain parallel and the correct distance apart under loading. In other words, the out of plane Young's modulus of cores should be high enough to provide stiff support for the faces of the sandwich structure. Second, because the faces of sandwich structures are relatively thin, most of the out of plane shear stress is carried by the core. Therefore the core must be stiff in out of plane shear. Third, the cores must be strong enough in the out of plane direction such that the cores do not buckle under compressive loads. Fourth, cores should be strong enough in out of plane shear that the core does not fail under out of plane shear loads. The out of plane shear strength of a core must be sufficient to carry the shear load caused by bending in the sandwich structure.

Four different core types are considered, three with 2-D isotropic patterns and finally 3-D isotropic foam cores. The three 2-D patterns are triangular cells, hexagonal cells and star shaped cells. The three cases show distinct characteristics as related to applications in sandwich structures.

The mechanical characteristics of three types of cores with two-dimensional isotropic patterns—triangular, hexagonal, and starcell—are studied both theoretically and experimentally. The Young's modulus, shear modulus, and Poisson's ratio are calculated for the three core types in the direction normal to the faces. The compressive buckling strength and shear buckling strength are calculated for the three core types by modeling each cell wall of the core as a plate under compressive or shear load. To verify the models, tests were conducted on scaled specimens to measure the compressive buckling strength of each core. The flexibilities of the three cores were also studied. Compliances for the three cores were measured using biaxial flexural tests. Tests were performed on each core type in which the deflection of a circular core sample loaded at its center was measured. The three isotropic core patterns exhibit distinct characteristics. In the direction normal to the faces, all three cores have the same stiffness. However, the triangular core has lower compressive and shear buckling strengths than the other two core types. The starcell core exhibits high flexibility compared to the other cores.

The buckling strengths of the three two-dimensional core types were found as given in Table 1.

Table 1

Out of plane normal buckling strengths and shear buckling strengths of three cores.

Core Types	σ_{cr}	τ_{cr}
Triangular core	$\frac{1}{9} \beta_n \frac{E_m}{1 - \nu_m^2} c^3$	$\frac{1}{9} \beta_s \frac{E_m}{1 - \nu_m^2} c^3$
Hexagonal core	$\beta_n \frac{E_m}{1 - \nu_m^2} c^3$	$\beta_s \frac{E_m}{1 - \nu_m^2} c^3$
Starcell core	$\beta_n \frac{E_m}{1 - \nu_m^2} c^3$	$\beta_s \frac{E_m}{1 - \nu_m^2} c^3$

where c is the volume fraction of material and where β_n and β_s are coefficients that only vary slightly depending on the boundary conditions at the edges of a single planar cell side. The experimental results were found to agree with the theoretical predictions.

The in-plane properties of the three two-dimensional core types, as predicted theoretically, are shown in Table 2.

Table 2
In-plane properties of three cores.

Core Types	$\frac{E_1}{E_m}$	$\frac{G_{12}}{E_m}$	$\frac{K}{E_m}$	ν_{12}
Triangular core	$\frac{1}{3} c$	$\frac{1}{8} c$	$\frac{1}{4} c$	$\frac{1}{3}$
Honeycomb core	$\frac{3}{2} c^3$	$\frac{3}{8} c^3$	$\frac{1}{4} c$	1
Starcell core	$\frac{9}{16} c^3$	$\frac{3}{16} c^3$	$\frac{9}{16} c^3$	$\frac{1}{2}$

Where the starcell form is seen to be much more flexible than the other two forms. The experimental results shown in Table 3 corroborated the theoretical comparisons shown in Table 2.

Table 3

Compliance measured by experiments for three cores.

Core Types	Compliances (inches/lb)
Triangular core	6.97×10^{-4}
Honeycomb core	7.86×10^{-4}
Starcell core	490×10^{-4}

The stiffness properties for a closed cell foam type core material are derived. The physical model is that of the generalized self consistent method. The resulting effective moduli are compared with those of the above described 2-D patterns. Trade-offs between 2-D isotropic pattern cores and 3-D isotropic foam cores are considered.

This work was performed with support from the Office of Naval Research, Dr. Y.D.S. Rajapakse as program monitor and under the auspices of the U.S. DOE for Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory under contract W-7405-Eng-48.

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